

Comparative Study of Lactomax Gold on Growth Performance of Broilers

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ABSTRACT:

A study was conducted in Cobb 430 broilers in western India. One thousand birds were allocated to four different treatments: Control, Competitor 1, Competitor 2, and the one supplemented with Lactomax Gold. After the completion of the trial, growth parameters like average body weight, feed intake, FCR, mortality, and EEF were analysed, and Lactomax Gold showed significantly better performance when compared to all the other treatments.

Keywords: Lactomax Gold, broilers, FCR, probiotics, prebiotics.

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INTRODUCTION

The application of antibiotics for disease control was later used as a practice to improve weight and feed efficiency in the case of broilers and named Antibiotic Growth Promoters (AGPs) [1,2,3,4]. People started reducing the use of antimicrobials (AGPs) in poultry production due to the emergence of drug-resistant bacteria, which adversely impacted public health [1,5,6,7]. Consequently, their use in animal feed has been prohibited in many countries [1,8,9].

Because of this, there is growing interest in finding new, affordable, and sustainable alternatives to antibiotics to improve growth, feed efficiency, and control of infectious diseases in poultry. Prebiotics, probiotics, enzymes, antimicrobial peptides (AMP), organic acids, bacteriophages, synbiotics, and phytogenic are a few of the antibiotic substitutes that have been studied and are currently being used in poultry [10,11,12]. Any alternatives used as a substitute for AGPs must ensure the preservation of gut health and the production of high-quality poultry [10,13]. Probiotics cover a wide range of microorganisms, including bacteria, yeast, fungi, cell fragments, and microbial secretions. [10,14,15]. These microbial strains must not be toxic or pathogenic, be advantageous to the host, be able to adhere to and colonise the intestinal mucosa, be antagonistic to pathogens, tolerate intestinal acids and bile salts, and be able to withstand intestinal contractions [10,16,17]. Prebiotics are non-living, fibrous feed additives that, when added to feed, encourage the growth of probiotics, thereby improving the health and performance of animals [18,19,20].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The present study was conducted in western India in the monsoon season on Cobb 430 broilers maintained under similar environmental conditions and fed on corn-soya-based diets. A total of 1000 birds were allocated to four different treatments, further divided into replicates. The treatments include a control group, group supplemented with competitor 1, group supplemented with competitor 2 and group supplemented with Lactomax Gold-WS in water 10g/1000 chicks in first water in the pre-starter period, Lactomax Gold-ME 100g/ton of feed in starter and finisher period the whole feed is mixed then Lactomax Gold-ME was added and pressed through pelleting machine and provided to the birds as pellet feed. The ingredient composition of pellet feed is mentioned in table I . Different growth parameters like Average weight gain, Feed Intake, FCR, Mortality and EEF were evaluated and interpreted using statistical procedures suggested by Snedecor and Cochran (1994) by applying one-way analysis of variance at a 95% confidence level [21].

Table1. Table Showing the Ingredient Composition of the Pellet Feed

Ingredients	Pre – starter (0-14)	Starter (15-28)	Finisher (29-35)
Maize	562.150	596.250	612.500
Soya DOC (45%)	377.100	330.100	299.100
OIL-Veg	16.250	26.000	36.500
De-oiled Rice Bran	5.000	9.000	10.000
L Lysine	3.650	3.200	3.000
DL Methionine	2.800	2.650	2.300
L Threonine	1.000	1.200	1.100
LSP powder	12.000	13.000	17.000
DCP	11.000	10.000	10.000
Salt	3.000	3.000	3.000
Soda bicarbonate	1.000	1.000	1.000
Phytase 5000	0.100	0.100	0.100
Broiler Vitamin Premix	0.500	0.500	0.500
Mineral mix	0.500	0.500	0.500
Toxin binder	1.000	1.000	1.000
Liver tonic	0.500	0.300	0.300
Choline Chloride, 60%	1.000	0.600	0.600
Coccidiostat	0.500	0.500	0.500
Acidifier	1.000	1.000	1.000
Lactomax Gold ME	-	0.100	0.100

RESULTS

Growth Parameters

After completion of the experiment, the Average body weight in the Lactomax Gold supplemented group (2470gms) was higher than that of Competitor 1 (2330gms), Competitor 2 (2124gms) groups and the Control group (2410gms), as shown in Fig 1. There is no significant difference in feed consumption in the Lactomax Gold supplemented group (4248.4gms) and the other groups Control (4262.1), Competitor 1(4217.3), Competitor 2(4248) as shown in Fig 1.

However, FCR was significantly improved in the Lactomax Gold supplemented group (1.72) when compared to the Control (1.81), Competitor 1 (1.81) and Competitor 2 (2). as shown in Fig 1. The mortality was significantly reduced in the Lactomax Gold supplemented group (3.5) followed by Competitor 1(3.52), Control (4.84) and Competitor 2 (5.13) groups, as shown in Fig 1. The EEF was highest in the Lactomax Gold supplemented group (324.7) followed by Control (301.6), Competitor 1 (295.7) and Competitor 2 (239.8), as shown in Fig 1.

A

Average Body Weight (g) at 42 days

B

Feed Intake (g)

C

FCR at 42 days

Figure 1. A. Average Body Weight at 42 days of age. B. Feed Intake C. FCR at 42 days of age. C. Mortality of the groups. D. EEF of the groups.

DISCUSSION

It is very crucial to select safe and appropriate antibiotic alternatives in poultry production that will give economic returns. The performance of broilers is often used to evaluate the influence of synbiotics on broiler chicken's health. In many experimental models, it has been shown that these nutritional supplements usually improve the performance of broiler chickens, but these results depend on the synbiotic used.

Growth performances including ABWG and FCR are the significant determinants used to assess the economic returns in broiler production [22]. In this study, ABWG in Lactomax Gold supplemented group was significantly higher. Moreover, the feed conversion ratio (FCR) was found to be improved considerably ($p < 0.001$) in probiotic-treated groups. These findings were in agreement with several published reports that increased BWG and ADWG in probiotic-supplemented feed [23,24]. According to Awad et al. [25], the improved growth performance in broilers might be due to the inclusion of synbiotics, which improved nutrient absorption and intestinal microbial ecology. Supplementation of probiotics will help secrete certain enzymes, improving the digestibility of nutrients and thereby enhancing feed utilisation and weight gain [26].

In our study, feed intake was not affected by supplementing Lactomax Gold. In line with our research, a study reported that feed intake was not affected by the supplementation of probiotics [27]. In contrast to our study, the feed intake was significantly improved by providing Probiotics due to the decreased gastric emptying time, while delivering Probiotics led to higher feed intake [28,29].

In the present study, we also evaluated the effect of dietary supplementation of Lactomax Gold and other competitor products on the mortality of Cobb 430 broilers. Interestingly, mortality was comparatively reduced in the Lactomax Gold supplemented group compared to different groups, proving the ability of prebiotics and probiotics to reduce mortality in broilers.

The reduction in mortality rate in the Lactomax Gold supplemented group might be attributed to the presence of surface adhesions (mucus-binding proteins) on the surface of probiotic bacteria [30], which mediate the attachment of probiotics with intestinal epithelial cells (IECs) and this interaction between probiotic bacteria and IECs may inhibit the colonisation of pathogenic bacteria in the intestinal mucosa [31] through competitive exclusion mechanism. Competitive exclusion by probiotic bacteria is based on their higher affinity to compete for available nutrients and adhesion sites on intestinal mucosa than gastrointestinal pathogens [32].

Prebiotics and probiotics supplementation will improve intestinal morphology, enhance immune response, and increase the concentration of SCFA, which will all aid in reducing mortality in broilers [33]. In addition, probiotic bacteria might induce the secretion of mucins [34] and β -defensins [35] from epithelial cells, which improve intestinal mucosal barrier functions, and it also secretes antimicrobial substances such as bacteriocins, which have a strong inhibitory effect against gastrointestinal pathogens [36].

The performance of broilers was also evaluated in terms of the European Production Efficiency Factor (EPEF), which includes daily weight gain and survival percentage. Higher values of EPEF indicate that the bird's body weight gain is uniform, and the flock is in good health [37]. The EPEF value in the Lactomax Gold supplemented group was significantly improved compared to the other groups.

CONCLUSION

The above study on broilers postulates that the Lactomax Gold provided at proper levels significantly improved overall growth performance in the Lactomax Gold supplemented group versus competitor products and Control. This finding offers significant practical applications regarding feed cost reduction, performance, efficiency improvements and sustainability. The combination of strategically selected probiotic strains and prebiotics proved beneficial. The birds showed significant improvements in average daily gain, Feed Intake, FCR, EEF and mortality compared to competitor product supplement groups. Based on the above results, Lactomax Gold is a better antibiotic replacement to improve the overall growth performance of broilers.

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